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Effects of Computer-Assisted Instruction on Performance in Programming Concepts among College of Education Computer Science Students in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the Effects of Computer Assisted Instruction on Performance in Programming Concepts among Colleges of Education Computer Science Students in North-West, Nigeria. The population of the study consists of 1204 (Male 695 and female 509) NCE II computer science students during 2024/25 academic session among colleges of education in Northwest, Nigeria. A sample size of 120 (60 male and 60 female) were selected from the target population using a multi-stage sampling technique. 60 students were used for Experimental and the remaining 60 for Control groups. Experimental group were taught using Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) package while control group were taught using lecture method of instruction. Four research questions and hypotheses respectively, were formulated to guide the study. Research questions were answered using descriptive statistics while hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics at 0.05 level of significance. Results obtained showed that students taught with CAI perform better than those taught with lecture method and CAI is also gender friendly. The study concluded that CAI should be encouraged as an effective assistance to both teacher and students for effective teaching and learning.

Keywords: Gender, Programming Concept, Performance and Computer Science Students

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Introduction

The concept of “gender” has attracted the attention of many researchers; biologist, mathematicians, psychologist and others. Gender difference is one of the factors affecting learning; studies on the influence of gender on students’ academic performance have not produced conclusive results. Some findings indicated that significant differences existed between the achievement of male and female students while other findings showed that gender factor has no influence on students’ achievement (Yusuf, 2004). In this study, the differential gender performance of computer science students in programming language skill using concept of “LOOP” is considered. Programming Languages according to French (2006), are languages used to program computer. They are computer languages designed to communicate instructions to a machine, particularly a computer.

This work therefore was conducted to investigate the gender difference in Programming concepts and Performance among Computer Science students in colleges of Education, north-west, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Several studies like Iwendi, 2009, Michael, Omiola and Mohammed (2014), Muchiri (2018), Achuonye (2018), Julious (2018), have been conducted in the area of gender-related differences in academic performance of students in sciences; some noted that males perform better (Iwendi, 2009, Muchiri, 2018), while another study reported females’ superiority in science subjects (Julious, 2018). Some claim no difference among gender (Michael, Omiola & Mohammed (2014), Achuonye, 2018). Poor performance of students in science related courses has also been of a thing of concern for decades of which most researchers claim that poor performance by students mostly, have to do with teaching method and strategies used by the teacher (Eze, Ezenwafor & Molokwu (2015), Ogunniyi, Akerele & Awoyemi, 2021); the concern in recent times is to have science classrooms that are student-centered, activity oriented and focuses on understanding rather than rote-learning and simple recall of knowledge. Again, our students, graduates from school without demonstrating high entrepreneurial skill in their various professions without undergoing serious training and/ or retraining (Ndukwe, P.E. 2016). The contradictive evidences in academic performance due to gender among others, had resulted in the need to verify how Computer Science Programming Test (CSPT) can influence students’ academic performance in computer

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programming concept by gender in computer science. The problem of the study is therefore, to find the Effects of Computer Assisted Instruction on Performance in Programming Concepts among Colleges of Education Computer Science Students in North-West, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to investigate the Effects of Computer Assisted Instruction on Performance in Programming Concepts among Colleges of Education Computer science students in North West, Nigeria. Specifically, to:

1. Ascertain the computer programming skill level of Federal Colleges of Education students when taught using Computer Assisted Instruction.
2. Investigate the computer programming skill level of male and female students of Federal Colleges of Education when exposed to Computer Assisted Instruction.
3. Determine the performance of Federal Colleges of Education students when taught using Computer Assisted Instruction.
4. Compare the performance of male and female students of Federal Colleges of Education when exposed to Computer Assisted Instruction.

Research Questions

1. What is the difference between the computer programming skill level of Federal Colleges of Education students taught computer science using the Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using the lecture method?
2. What is the difference between the computer programming skill level of Federal Colleges of Education male and female students taught computer science using the Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught by the lecture method?
3. What is the difference between the mean performance score of Federal Colleges of Education students when taught computer science using Computer Assisted Instruction and when taught by lecture method?
4. What is the difference between the mean performance score of Federal Colleges of Education male and female students when taught computer science using Computer Assisted Instruction and when taught by the lecture method?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

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Ho₁: There is no significant difference between computer programming skill level of Federal Colleges of Education students when taught Computer Science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught by the lecture method.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between computer programming skill level of male and female Federal Colleges of Education students when taught Computer Science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught by the lecture method.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of students of Federal Colleges of Education taught Computer Science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using the lecture method.

Ho₄: There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of male and female students of Federal Colleges of Education taught Computer Science using the Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using the lecture method.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was the quasi-experimental research design, involving two groups, one experimental and one control. Both groups were pretested each on Programming concept and performance before the administration of treatment to ensure equivalence in level of performance in the experimental groups only; while students in the control group were taught using the lecture method and a Posttest administered after treatment to all groups of students to determine their performance

Population of the study

The population of the study comprised of NCE II Students of Computer Science Education in five Federal Colleges of Education in North West, Nigeria.

S/NO	COLLEGES	NCE 2 MALE	COMPUTER SCIENCE FEMALE	TOTAL
1	Federal College of Education Kano	173	78	251
2	Federal College of Education Katsina	74	75	149
3	Federal College of Education Zaria	232	170	402

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4	Federal College of Education (T) Bichi	216	108	324
5	Federal College of Education (T) Gusau	0	78	78

TOTAL		695	509	1,204
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Departmental records, 2023/2024 academic sessions

Sample and Sampling Techniques

Two (2) colleges were selected using simple multi-stage sampling technique from the five (5) Federal Colleges of Education: they are Federal College of Education, Zaria (FCEZ) and Federal College of Education (Technical) (FCE(T)), Bichi. Five Subject combinations were sampled by the simple random sampling (balloting) from the seven combinations available in the colleges namely: Mathematic/Computer, Chemistry/Computer, Physics/Computer, Biology/Computer and Economics/Computer. Six students were then selected using the simple random sampling comprising of three male and three female computer Science students from each of the five computer combinations. This gives sixty (60) students per selected college; thirty (30) male and thirty (30) female students. This gives a total of 120 students and according to Tuckman (1975) and Sambo (2008), the Central Limit Theorem recommended a minimum of 30 ($N \geq 30$) subjects for experimental study of this nature. Hence the sample of 120 students is viable for this study. Equal number of male and female students, (60 for both male and female) for the research was used to avoid gender bias.

Instrumentation

Two validated instruments were used to collect data for the study; Computer Science Performance Test (CSPT) with reliability coefficient of 0.83 when subjected to Pearson Product Moment of Correlation and the Computer Science Computer Programming Concept Inventory (CPLSI) with a Cronbach value of 0.75 which ascertained their reliabilities. The instruments were validated by two senior Computer Science lecturers who have taught Programming Languages for over ten years in colleges of Education.

Data Analysis

Research questions were answered using descriptive statistics while hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics at 0.05 level of significance

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Presentation of Result

Research Question 1

What is the difference between the computer programming skill level of Federal Colleges of Education students taught computer science using the Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method?

Table 1: Mean Rank scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean Rank		Mean Rank Difference
		Pretest	Posttest	
Experimental	60	40.95	77.43	36.48
Control	60	40.05	43.57	3.52

From Table 1, the experimental group had a higher mean rank (posttest) Computer Programming skill level score of 77.43 compared to that of the control group who had 43.57. Also, it was observed that the mean rank difference of the experimental and control groups was 36.48 and 3.52 respectively.

Null Hypothesis 1

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between computer programming skill level of Federal Colleges of Education students when taught Computer Science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method.

This hypothesis was analyzed using Mann-Whitney U-test as presented in Tables 2.

Table 2: Summary of Mann-Whitney U-Test of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	U-value	P-value	Remark
Experimental Group	60	77.43	4921.50	508.50	0.001*	S
Control	60	43.57	2338.50			
Total	120					

*Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

Table 2 revealed that the Mann-Whitney U-value of 508.50 produced a corresponding P-value of 0.001 which was significant at $P \leq 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is significant difference between the Computer Programming skill level of students taught computer science using the Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) and those taught using the lecture method.

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Research Question 2

What is the difference between the computer programming skill level of Federal Colleges of Education male and female students taught computer science using the Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method?

Table 3: Mean Rank Skills Scores of Male and Female Students in the Experimental and Control Groups

Group	Sex	N	Mean Rank		Mean Rank Difference
			Pretest	Posttest	
Experimental	Male	30	41.95	85.32	43.37
	Female	30	40.55	84.62	44.07
Control	Male	30	43.23	65.95	22.72
	Female	30	42.90	57.18	14.28

The summary of mean Computer Programming skill Level score presented in Table 3 revealed a mean rank (posttest) score of 85.32 and 84.62 respectively for male and female students in the experimental group. In the control group, the mean rank (posttest) score for male and female students was found to be 22.72 and 14.28 respectively. However, the mean rank difference Computer Programming skill level score for the male and female students in both groups was higher for the experimental group (43.37 and 44.07). The control group was observed to have lower mean rank difference (22.72 and 14.28).

Null Hypothesis 2

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between computer programming skill level of male and female Federal Colleges of Education students when taught Computer Science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method.

Table 4: Summary of Kruskal-Wallis H-test for Gender between Experimental and Control Groups

Groups	Sex	N	Mean Rank	H-value	p-value	Remarks
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Experimental	Male	30	85.90	46.97	0.001*	S
	Female	30	84.62			
Control	Male	30	65.95			
	Female	30	57.18			

*Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

Table 4 revealed that a Kruskal-Wallis H-value of 46.97 has a corresponding P-value of 0.001 which was significant at $P \leq 0.05$. Hence, the hypothesis 4 was rejected. This implied that there was a significant difference in the Computer Programming skill level of the groups with respect to gender. In order to ascertain where the difference lied, the data was subjected to the Dunn-Bonferroni post hoc test of multiple comparisons and presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Dunn-Bonferroni post hoc test of Multiple Comparison for Gender between the Experimental and Control Group

Group	Mean Difference	Std Error	P-Value	Remarks
Female control group - Male control group	0.917	8.956	0.918	NS
Female control group - Male Exp. Group	39.633	8.956	0.001	S
Female control group - Female Exp. Grp	47.383	8.956	0.001	S
Male control group - Male Exp. Group	38.717	8.956	0.001	S
Male control group - Female Exp. Group	46.467	8.956	0.001	S
Male Exp. Group - Female Exp. Group	-7.75	8.956	0.387	NS

Table 5 showed that the difference in computer science students Computer Programming Concept was not significant for male and female students of control group and male and female of experimental group. This implied that Computer Assisted Instruction Method of Instruction and lecture method are all gender friendly.

Research Question 3

What is the difference between the mean performance score of Federal Colleges of Education students when taught computer science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method?

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Table 6: Descriptive Statistics of Performance of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean	S.D
Experimental group	60	56.25	13.62
Control group	60	45.13	7.44
Total	120		

From Table 6, experimental group had a mean score of 56.25 with a corresponding standard deviation score of 13.62 and the control group had a mean score of 45.13 and standard deviation score of 7.44 respectively.

Null Hypothesis 3

Ho₃: There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of students of Federal Colleges of Education taught Computer Science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method.

Table 7: t-test Analysis of Performance between Exp. Group and Control Group

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Experimental Group	60	56.25	13.62	58	5.55	0.001*	S
Control Group	60	45.13	7.44				

*Significant at P ≤ 0.05

From Table 7, the p-value 0.001 with its corresponding t-value of 5.55 showed that there is significant difference between experimental group taught with Computer Assisted Instruction and the control group taught with lecture method at P ≤ 0.05 level of significant. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This showed that there was significant difference between the performance of students taught computer science with Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught with lecture method of instruction.

Research Question 4

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What is the difference between the mean performance score of Federal Colleges of Education male and female students when taught computer science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method?

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics of Gender of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	Sex	N	Mean	SD
Experiment Group	Male	30	55.20	15.63
	Female	30	57.30	11.45
Control	Male	30	44.50	7.71
	Female	30	45.77	7.23
Total		120		

From Table 8, the mean score and standard deviation of male students of Experimental group were 55.20 and 15.63 while the mean score and standard deviation of the female students of the experimental group were 57.30 and 11.45. For the control group, the mean score and standard deviation score of the female students taught with lecture method were found to be 45.77 and 7.23 respectively while the mean score and standard deviation of their male counterpart were 44.50 and 7.71.

Null Hypothesis 4

Ho₄: There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of male and female students of Federal Colleges of Education taught Computer Science using the Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method.

Table 9: Analysis of variance for Gender between Experimental and Control Groups

	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	Df	t-value	P-value	Remark
Between Groups	3797.63	8877.58	3	10.39	0.001*	S
Within Groups	5232.25	68.85				
Total	31864.99					

*Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

From Table 9 the p-value 0.001 with its corresponding t-value of 10.39 showed that there is significant difference between the experimental group taught with Computer Assisted Instruction and control group taught with lecture method at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significant. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This showed that there was

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significant difference between the performance of computer students taught with Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught with lecture method of instruction.

To ascertain where the difference lied, the data was subjected to Scheffes post hoc test.

Table 10: Scheffes Post hoc comparison test of Gender of Exp. and Control Group

(I) Gender	(J) Gender	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	P-value	Remark
Male Exp. Group	Female Exp. Group	-2.10	2.849	0.909**	NS
	Male Cont. group	10.70	2.849	0.004*	S
	Female Cont. group	9.43	2.849	0.015**	NS
Female Exp. Group	Male Exp. Group	2.10	2.849	0.909**	NS
	Male control group	12.80	2.849	0.001*	S
	Female control group	11.53	2.849	0.002*	S
Male control group	Male Exp. Group	-10.70	2.849	0.004*	S
	Female Exp. Group	-12.80	2.849	0.001*	S
	Female control group	-1.27	2.849	0.978**	NS
Female control group	Male Exp. Group	-9.43	2.849	0.015**	NS
	Female Exp. Group	-11.53	2.849	0.002*	S
	Male control group	1.27	2.849	0.978**	NS

*Significant at $P \leq 0.05$, **Not Significant at $P \leq 0.05$,

From Table 10, it was observed that there was no significant different between performance of male and female computer science students of Experimental group (0.909). It was also observed that the performance of male and female computer science students of control group was not significant. This means that CAI and Lecture method of Instruction are gender friendly.

Discussion of Findings

The result in Table 1 showed that there is a difference between the mean ranks of the Programming skill level of experimental and control group in favour of the experimental group. The result was then subjected to Mann-Whitney U-test; it was observed that there was significant mean Computer Programming skill level difference between the students taught with Computer Assisted Instruction method and those taught with

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lecture method of Instruction. This confirms Ifeakor (2005) finding that level of activities involved in learning can improve students learning outcomes; she suggested that manipulating the computer involve some activities and also interesting. Muoneme (2012) opined that instructional package usage in learning motivates students and is a key variable in education as supported by Okoroma (2000), Moris and Aggawal (2007) who added that computer-based instructions not only motivate students' interest but also stimulates several senses thus making the learner more involved consequently setting the students excitement and desire to put in their best during learning.

In Table 3, the respective mean ranks and sum ranks of experimental group compared with that of control group showed that there was higher gender Computer Programming skill level in favour of the experimental group. This was further subjected to Kruskal Wallis H-Test in Table 4. The findings showed that the observed difference in Computer Programming Concept was significant within the two groups. This is supported by research conducted by Balogun (2004), Michael and Rahman (2001) that showed higher skill acquisition when Computer Assisted Instruction is used as learning strategy. This also is in line with the study carried out by Gongden and Gongden (2019), who observed that using CAI in learning improve both male and female learners.

From Table 6, which sought to answer research question three, the students exposed to CAI mode of instruction had a higher mean gain compared with that of the control group. This was found to be in favour of the experimental group which implied that the use of Computer Assisted Instruction learning strategy improved students' academic performance in computer science. The finding was in line with that of Tabassum (2004) who revealed that overall performance of students taught by lecture method, supplemented by Computer Assisted Instruction package, is higher than those taught with lecture method only. It was also supported by Akour (2008) and Ndukwe (2016), who revealed the fact, that lecture method together with computer Assisted Instruction enhances performance.

Table 8 revealed that female students of the experimental group performed better than the male students when CAI was administered. Comparison within the groups was carried out using Analysis of Variance and was subjected to Scheffes post hoc test to ascertain where the difference lied. There was no significance difference in the performance of male and female students taught Computer Science using CAI. This implies that CAI is a gender friendly method for Computer Science Pedagogy. This is in

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line with the findings of Michael, Omiola & Mohammed (2014), Achuonye (2018) who found from their research that Computer Assisted Instruction is gender friendly.

Conclusion

It can be adduced from the findings of this study that in the area of performance, experimental group with use of CAI model (CSPT) of instruction performed significantly better compared with those exposed to Lecture mode of instruction. CAI was observed to improve students Computer Programming skill in Computer Science better than the lecture method only. Hence, CAI should be encouraged as an effective assistance to both teacher and students for effective teaching and learning irrespective of gender.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are offered based on the outcome of this study:

1. Colleges of Education in Nigeria as well as other institutions of higher learning should endeavour to incorporate the development and use of CAI for effective teaching and learning to enhance students' performance in computer science and science related courses in colleges of education.
2. Curriculum planners and school managements should rely on flexible home-based CAI packages as a gender friendly strategy for learning. for better development of education and other sectors in Nigeria.

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